

The Interactionalist Classroom Management - A Way to Reduce the Behaviour Problems in the Classroom

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Abstract : Classroom management is a teacher's attitude and action which help him to manage classroom activities, specially student behavior. A teacher's approach to classroom management may be classified as interventionist, noninterventionist, or interactionalist. This paper tries to analyze interactionalist belief of teachers and subsequent behaviour, important models/ theories under interactionalist approach and bring forth some strategies of interactionalist approach of classroom management which can decrease classroom problems.

Key words : classroom management, interactionalist approach.

Introduction

Classroom management is an important task of a teacher for effective teaching and learning in the classroom. It is established that a well managed classroom is prerequisite to learning and it can create a favourable learning environment in the classroom. Wang, Haertel and Walberg (1993) demonstrated that among 228 variables (which come under 30 categories within 6 theoretical constructs), classroom management as a category under theoretical

construct of classroom practices had the largest effect on students achievement. Their study clearly make a sense that student can not learn well in a chaotic, poorly managed classroom. Marzano, Marazano and Pickering (2003) believe that teachers role as a classroom manager is important in terms of effective teaching and learning in a classroom. In a poorly managed classroom, smooth flow of teaching - learning activities are disrupted due to disorderly and disrespectful students. If there is no rules,

procedure and guidance of the expected behavior in the classroom, chaos is the only resultant. In this situation, both teachers and students suffer - teachers struggle to teach and students to learn. Classroom management is the teacher's attitude and action that influence students' behaviour in the classroom. It is a teacher's efforts to manage classroom activities such as learning, interaction, and student behavior. A teacher's approach to classroom management may be classified as interventionist, noninterventionist, or interactionist (Martin & Baldwin, 1994).

The Interactionist Teacher Behaviour

Woolfolk and Weinstein (2006) maintained that the teachers who believe students' misbehaviours are due to 'inabilities to manage their own internal needs in relation to the external pressures of classroom life,' behave to manage classroom in a socializing manner (p.194). These teachers help the students to understand the nature and importance of external pressures (i.e. tasks and rules in the classrooms). For managing the classroom, interactionist teachers emphasize on the interaction with the students to establish shared goal and standards. The interactionist teachers believe in Confronting-Contracting Philosophy which suggests sharing of power with the students for behavioural change. This philosophy favours an adult relationship with a misbehaving student by requesting the student to stop and change. According to Glickman and Wolfgang (1979), the interactionist teacher views that child develops from the concurrent actions of inward unfolding and conditioning with outer forces. The child must be aware of such behaviour which is socially acceptable and teacher has to constantly

interact with the child. Glickman and Wolfgang (1979) say, "The interactionist theory of coping with child behavior is based on the teacher's ability to be a clarifier, boundary delineator, and finally an enforcer. These theorists believe that the child should take responsibility for his/her actions but needs the active involvement of a firm, though kind, teacher. The child and/or teacher may decide on the remedy. Regardless of action, a solution acceptable to all must result" (P.8). Martin and Sass (2010) say "... interactionists focus on what the individual does to alter the external milieu, as well as what the environment does to shape the individual. Interactionists work to find solutions acceptable to both the teacher and the students...." (p.?)

The Interactionist Models/Theories

On the basis of interactionist ideology theorists like Dreikurs, Glasser and Gathercoal have developed their own theory/model of classroom management. These theories/models are Democratic Teaching and Management, Choice Theory, Judicious Discipline.

Democratic Teaching & Management

The propounder of Democratic Teaching and Management model of classroom management is Rudolf Dreikurs. There are four key concepts underlying Dreikurs theory of Democratic Teaching and Management; the concepts are: i) Mistaken Goals (all misbehaviour results when students have one or more of the following mistaken goals for their behaviour: attention getting, power seeking, revenge and helplessness); ii) Democratic Teaching (teacher should be democratic rather than autocratic or permissive in their classroom procedures and

social interaction with the students); iii) Encouragement (teacher should encourage students rather than praise the students); iv) Logical Consequences (teacher should establish classroom rules and implement logical consequences rather than punishments for broken rules and misbehaviours.

Dreikurs believed that people have the capacity to develop their social interest and they are motivated to interact with others. The inborn ability to interact with other people should be nurtured in childhood days which makes a society healthy and the school has the responsibility to develop social interests within the children and develop the sense of belongingness, make them feel valued, develop positive self-worth. (Prior & Tollerud, 1999)

Dreikurs favoured democratic teaching and management for developing a caring and nurturing environment in schools. He viewed democracy as the mean for all-round development for all members of a society.

Dreikurs opines that the teacher has to know more than the subject matter to become an effective one and s/he has to develop democratic classroom and use effective instructional strategies for these purposes. S/he must commit to several beliefs: the belief in the worth and dignity of every person; the belief in freedom of decision making; and the belief that people can make wise decisions (Dreikurs, 1968).

To be an effective democratic teacher, Manning and Bucher (2007) suggested some management tips – teachers can develop a democratic classroom by -

i) treating students as individuals and with respect during all teaching and management situations, ii) modelling respect at all times, such

as speaking respectfully, encouraging rather than praising, and avoiding punishments, iv) developing self-respect needed to be a professional educator and to respect others, v) allowing students to help make important decisions, vi) using instructional methods that meet individual student's learning needs & interests.

Dreikurs (1968) accepted the basic idea of Alfred Adler that all behaviour – including misbehaviour – is orderly and purposeful and directed towards achieving social recognition. Edwards (2008) opines, “Our culture does not furnish sufficient means for children to achieve this recognition. In many children, the desire for attention goes unfulfilled. When children solicit recognition without success they usually misbehave to gain it. All misbehaviour is the result of a child's mistaken assumption about how to find a place and gain status” (P.98).

Dreikers (1968) has identified four mistaken goals which indulge individuals to commit misbehaviour. These goals are i) gaining attention ii) exercising power iii) exacting revenge iv) displaying inadequacy. According to Edwards (2008), these mentioned goals have a hierarchical relationship to one another. Children first try to achieve recognition and status through strategies designed to gain them. If these strategies don't work, the children employ power. Power may be followed by revenge; finally children use inadequacy as an excuse when earlier strategies have proven unsuccessful (P.98). The four mistaken goals may be summarily described as follows:-

i) Gaining Attention

When students feel they are worthless, then often misbehave to get the attention they want.

This behaviour might be more dominant in young children who feel they have few opportunities to establish their social positions through useful contributions, or through socially accepted means.

ii) Exercising Power

When children fail to gain all the attention they seek, they often engage in a power struggle with parents and teachers. According to Prior and Tollerud (1999), the students who are seeking power, their behaviour becomes more defiant and includes disobedience. In the condition of power exercising, teachers should avoid putting pressure on these children in an effort to help them behave properly, because exerting pressure on students may lead power contest.

iii) Exacting Revenge

When children's efforts are dissatisfied, they usually deal with unfair manner. They believe that revenge is important for their own self-esteem. To feel important and valuable the students believe they must hurt someone in the same manner as someone has hurt them. Commonly they take out their revenge on anyone around them. They are certain that nobody liked them and make proof of this dislike by provoking others to strike back. In this situation, teachers must offer understanding and assistance because causing them more pain will only provoke more revenge seeking behaviour.

iv) Displaying Inadequacy

Children who fail to achieve a sense of self worth through attention, power or revenge often become so disheartened that they give up and seek wrap themselves in a group of

inadequacies. These children strive to be left alone because they attempt to retain what little self-esteem they have left by avoiding any kind of public display. The display of inadequacy is their desperate effort to reach these ultimate goals of being accepted for what one is, even if one is inadequate.

Dreikurs, Grunwald & Pepper (1982) maintained that it is imperative that a teacher need to understand children's behaviour, their mistaken goals from a psychological point of view. Democratic Teaching and Management model has accepted students as social beings who want to fit in the society. This model favours to identify the goals of the misbehaviours committed by the students, rather imposing punishment or rewards in reaction to the students' behaviour.

Teacher's key action for managing his classroom is to use democratic procedures, s/ he has to encourage students to take an active, and participatory role in developing classroom procedure as well as curricular and instructional decisions. Logical Consequences is another important component of Dreikurs model which becomes easier to teacher after establishing classroom rules and procedure. Dreikurs believed that the practice of establishing rules and logical consequence developed with the help of students could prevent discipline problem because students have worked co-operatively to establish their own rules and procedure. (Morris, 1996).

According to Dreikurs model, teachers should use more encouragement & less praise. Because encouragement boost the students' confidence and self esteem, where as praise make them praise dependent. When praise is used, if students do not continue the behaviour

or fail to achieve the goal, they begin to think they are of less worth. In essence, the reason for the praise becomes the source of self-worth. When the reason for the praise decreases; the students feeling of self-worth also go down. (Manning & Bucher, 2007)

Democratic Classroom Management Model has the potentiality to be applied in schools at all levels. In a learning centred environment, prevailing in the classroom requires teachers and students work together toward a common purpose and teacher can use democratic classroom approaches which help the students understand the goals of misbehaviour, the effect of logical consequences and the importance of social interaction. The important element of Dreikurs model is need for rules and order, student participation in the development of classroom rules, development of the spirit of trust and co-operation with a democratic teacher and the use of encouragement in classroom. "Unlike the Canters, Assertive Discipline, Democratic Teaching and Management do not include check marks for misbehaviour for a hierarchy of discipline procedure. But it does demand is for effective teachers to have a genuine commitment to democratic classrooms, logical consequences and the use of encouragement". (Manning & Bucher, 2007, p.71).

Dreikurs's model has certain advantages. It promotes respect and communication among teachers and students to take responsibilities for their own behaviour, to establish classrooms. It influences the instructional practice of teachers, the logical consequences. It helps to promote a degree of autonomy for students and helps students to correct their behaviour. Dreikurs's emphasis on understanding of causes of behaviour can contribute to making schools safer

for students as well as for teachers. Dreikurs believed that discipline should be taught, rather than imposed and argues that it is an ongoing process. He believed, once students learn the reason for misbehaviour, they are in a better position to learn self-discipline and to apply that discipline on themselves. Dreikurs's model encourages the student to engage in self-discipline and learn to demonstrate appropriate behaviour.

Choice Theory

In addition to serving in the US Army William Glasser also worked as a psychiatric consultant. Glasser is well known for his Reality Therapy and Control Theory. But his Choice Theory is the most relevant with respect to classroom management. Glasser (1997) believed that students have specific human needs and motives. They should be responsible for their own behavior. According to Glasser (1997), the Choice Theory is based upon the belief that we can only control our own behavior. The psychology of external control destroys human relationship and prevents individuals from being close to each other. Choice Theory explains that adults and children chose to do every thing they do. From birth to death, people behave in specific ways based upon their choice of behavior or what they think is most appropriate at the time. (Clark, 2003)

As we can control only the behavior of our own, so the close relationship between teacher and a student lead to a change in the student's maladaptive or destructive behavior. Manning and Bucher (2007) mentioned that, "To Glasser, students (as well as all people) are driven by five basic psychological needs: the need for survival, the need to belong, the need for power,

the need for freedom and the need for fun. Once teachers meet these psychological needs, students will choose to demonstrate appropriate behavior. Likewise, when teachers fail to meet students' psychological needs, misbehaviors result. Using coercion or external control, whether rewards or punishment (such as abuse, violence, nagging, or complaining) is harmful because, the students are not choosing their behavior, they are changing behavior to get the reward or to avoid punishment. Glasser believes that coercion does not work and should be replaced with Choice Theory" (p.36).

Glasser made several contributions to classroom management. He believed that students think rationally, but teachers still require to make and enforce rules and when necessary, impose proper consequences and give suggestions for inappropriate behavior. He called for educators to make schools into caring places where students experience fun and where they feel a sense of belongingness. The educators have the responsibility to help the students, satisfy their five psychological needs so that they will be more likely to choose appropriate behavior. The educators can allow students to participate in making class rules and determining acceptable behaviour in the classroom, can use bulletin boards in the classroom, library and other location or even walls of the classrooms to display the work of all students for developing belongingness in the students.

Judicious Discipline

The Judicious Discipline of classroom management was developed by Forrest Gathercoal, who had experience as a classroom teacher, high school vice-principal in the public schools. Gathercoal (2001) believes that

remember rules is more difficult than to accept and abide by a moral and ethical code that consist of a few principles that guide behaviour. Gathercoal based his Judicious Discipline on the rule that students may do whatever they wish in a classroom until their behaviour interfere with the right of others. Here students are entitled to enjoy freedom but freedom does not mean that students have the permit to do according to their pleasure but it means students have freedom to think and act according to their own self interest including balance with the welfare needs of others. Edward (2008) opined that students must understand the meaning of freedom, justice and equality. Students must realize that they have a responsibility to others in the community. As freedom is restricted, so the students should use freedom to such extent that there should be an appropriate balance between one's personal right and the needs and interest of the others.

Gathercoal (2001) believed that educators should always practice professional ethics by modelling acceptable standards of moral and proper conduct. Gathercoal (2001) described Judicious Discipline as a management style based on the synthesis of professional ethics, good educational practice, and students' constitutional rights and responsibilities. Wolfgang (2001) says, "Judicious Discipline, however, basically is a reflective and teaching model requiring the teacher to cognitively think out her general approach and pass nearly all school practices through the filter of democratic rights"(p-186).

Manning and Bucher (2007) commented that while implementing Judicious Discipline teacher should introduce students to the rights encompassed in the concept of freedom, justice and equality. This process includes creating a

democratic school environment in which every teacher models these three values. Teachers should create an equitable learning environment where every student has the opportunity to win and teach students to be leaders because student-leadership leads to a positive outcome for class, school and society as a whole. Gathercoal (2001) opined that teachers have a responsibility to develop democratic classroom in which students know that their human rights are secured.

Edward (2008) opines that professional ethics of the teachers are the conscience of a school community and provide standards for moral conduct and these encourage teachers to act in the interest of students. Teachers should avoid saying and doing such things which cause students feel unaccepted. Students must not only feel accepted but they must believe their teachers are consistently providing experiences for their intellectual, social and psychological development.

Gathercoal (2001) contends that teachers can engage students in discussion about their statement of ethics and provide students opportunity to react and express their opinion. This may built greater trust in students and more responsible learning conditions can be established. For adoption of Judicious Discipline, teachers should focus on the professional ethics, a constitutional perspective to school rule with judicious consequences and development of a democratic classroom. Teachers need to develop and teach rules and expectations for behaviour through class discussion, group activities and class meetings, in which classroom conflicts can be resolved peacefully. To demonstrate professional ethics, educators generally act accordingly through daily interaction with

students. Gathercoal (2001) emphasised a teacher's personal code of ethics, student centeredness in all interactions with students and avoidance of negative disciplinary practices which are the important components of a teacher's interaction behaviour with the students. He also suggested that all educators should draft and post their personal statement for code of ethics, so that the students and other teachers can realize the ethics by which the educator tries to live. These statements indicate the acceptable standards of student conduct and the belief of an educator to act in the best interest of the students. Gathercoal (2001) believed that teachers' professional and ethical beliefs should show their student centeredness. Every interaction with misbehaving students should centre on the resolution of the problem by helping the students to grow and to recover from mistakes. Manning and Bucher (2007) opine that the daily activities of all educators are guided by their conscious or unconscious beliefs in some fundamental moral principles. But, unfortunately, a difference often exists between what a person says is an ethical thing to do and what that person does when an ethical problem occurs. Until a person experience a situation, he never can be sure exactly how he will behave.

Gathercoal (2001) calls for a democratic classroom community which creates a culture of freedom of movement and nurtures confidence, trust and consciousness. Here, the democratic classrooms will be such that recognize and establish the principles of human rights. In a democratic classroom, school rules should be kept to a minimum and students should be involved in the rule-making process and they should learn that there is an appropriate time, place, and manner for exercising their individual

rights. If students develop class rules in a democratic community, the students learn the skills of responsibility and self-motivation.

Educators use consequences to encourage, convince or compel students to behave appropriately. When it is necessary to have consequence for misbehaviours, judicious discipline favours for the adoption of judicious consequences, which is a teacher's behaviour with more professional relationship and the use of individual consequences that keeps in mind the students' best interest and what the student can learn from the incident. There are two important aspects in judicious consequences –i) the consequence must be commensurate with the violation, ii) the consequence must be compatible with needs and interests of the student and the school community. When consequences are commensurate, students are more likely to accept them as appropriate and to learn more acceptable behaviours and better attitudes. The compatible consequences represent a broad view of the problem and include attention to students' need including personal self worth and academic achievement (Edwards, 2008).

According to Gathercoal (2001), the first word spoken to a student who has misbehaved should be in the form of a question. It helps the teacher to avoid harsh statements and to send message that he is working in the students' best interest and give the students' power in the relationship. Questions also can encourage students to talk about the problems, discuss about the problem and talking about what they have done. Teachers can avoid questions like 'why have you misbehaved?' Instead they can use 'what happened?' or 'Can I help you?' or 'Would you like to talk about the problem?' If

students are willing to discuss their problems, they are ready to accept the ownership of the problem and if properly handled should become accountable for their actions. In contrast, students who do not respond immediately to questions or refuse to discuss about the problem, might need more time to process their feelings. When students break rules, teachers need to interact in such a way that students must believe that their feelings and opinions are valued and the teacher wants to help them, rather than use punishment. If a student breaks a rule a teacher should ask the student, 'what needs to be learned from breaking the rule for changing the future goals and attitudes?'

Good discipline depends on teachers' effort to give value to their students as persons and respect students' ability to make wise judgement about rules and consequences. When students are effectively involved in making rules they will achieve the level of ownership of democratic principles operated in the classroom. In applying judicious discipline to classrooms, teachers must help students to learn the implications of constitutional right and principles, not only for a life generally, but also for life in the classroom.

Several authors proposed class meetings as a means of giving students a voice in class decisions as well as helping students resolve their interpersonal conflicts. In class meetings, students can deal with undesired behaviours or arrive at peaceful conflict resolution. Democratic class meetings are an essential part for the effective operation of judicious discipline. Because these contribute to the sharing of power and the avoidance of power struggles as all students have opportunities to express their concerns, students learn skills of conflict

resolutions in all aspects of their life. It is to be kept in mind that when students feel they have power in class operation, they are less likely to misbehave.

Landau and P. Gathercoal (2000) stated that judicious discipline coupled with class meeting promote good citizenship and safe, productive learning environments. When used in combination with another, more refined classroom management model, Judicious Discipline has the potential to address many of the problems those the schools face today. This model provides students a more suitable sense of how violation of their rights may be addressed. It helps students learn to balance their rights against compelling school interest and get a true picture of their rights and responsibilities in a democratic society. This model does not wait for problems to occur rather it prevents problem by framing classroom rules and resolving classroom conflicts peacefully in a democratic environment. It encourages students for higher order thinking skills through real social situation as students are invited to describe, explain, predict and make choices. It minimizes classroom stress and anxiety for both students and teachers due to emphasis on human rights and individual dignity. Gathercoal (2001) observed that much of the success of Judicious Discipline comes from teachers' ability to trust their students, teaching them the concepts of rights and responsibilities and acting in ways consistent with civil responsibility.

The interactionalist strategies

The analysis of above mentioned three models has put forth some strategies of classroom management which can be called as

interactionalist strategies. The strategies are as follows-

- i) Allow students to participate in developing class rules and procedures and determining acceptable behaviour in the classroom.
- ii) Use bulletin board or class wall to display the work of all students for developing sense of belongingness.
- iii) Engage all the students in working together by means of peer tutoring or cooperative learning so that all students can know their classmates.
- iv) Obtain commitment by all the students for rules and procedures those were decided on.
- v) Identify the mistaken goal(s) which reflect(s) the misbehaviour of students.
- vi) Prepare classroom rules and their logical consequences democratically with the active participation of students instead of set punishment for behaviour in general.
- vii) Encourage students instead of praising a student (Like: praise-"well-done! You finished your math in record time." encouragement-"you have been practicing math and I hope you will continue."
- viii) Post personal statement or code of ethics on the wall or bulletin board which are indication of acceptable standards of students conduct.
- ix) When student's misbehaviour occurs, ask student 'what happened' or 'can I

help you?’ in stead of ‘why have you misbehaved?’

- x) When a student breaks a rule; ask the student, what needs to be learned from breaking the rule, for changing his future goals and attitudes.
- xi) Treat students with respect, dignity, friendliness and kindness and allow students to help in making class decisions.
- xii) Gain the attention of the students by appropriate techniques while they are in much freedom and talk too much.
- xiii) Demonstrate ethical practices those make a teacher student centered and make students feel secure.
- xiv) Make the students understand their right and respect the rights of others to make classroom democratic.
- xv) Organise class meeting to resolve interpersonal conflicts and avoid power struggles.

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Conclusions

Interactionalist classroom management emphasizes democracy in the classroom. Shared responsibility is an important feature of interactionalist classroom management. It makes the students self-reliant, make them responsible for their own behaviour and help them in sharing

of power which automatically decreases the management problems. The teachers who possess interactionalist belief may adopt the strategies and thereby relevant techniques to make their classroom problem-free which ultimately help the teacher and the students to teach and learn well respectively. But there should be reservation that the interactionalist strategies to be adopted in classroom require awareness and sincerity of teachers and training may improve teachers’ ability to practice those strategies under interactionalist approach of classroom management.

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